

TEACHING DIFFERENT TYPES OF ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION

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Abstract: Teaching English pronunciation is a challenging task with different objectives at each level. Teaching pronunciation is an area of language teaching that many English teachers avoid. While there are many textbooks and instruction manuals available, there is comparatively little on learning pronunciation.

Keywords: pronunciation, spoken interaction, sociolinguistic, predicting, foundations, phonetic.

Pronunciation work has traditionally taken a secondary role in language teaching to work on grammar and more recently lexis. Today English is a world language; it is spoken by millions both as first and second language almost all over the world. The varieties best known to people are British and American English. Another variety of English, which is spoken by both native and non-native speakers, is a mixture of British English and American English called Mid-Atlantic English. Attitudes and prejudice amongst pupils and their teachers towards these two varieties are looked into as well as whether the pupils speak the variety of English they claim they speak. The question of why the pupils speak the variety they do is also investigated. The results show that most pupils mix British and American English and that American English features predominate in the mix. According to this investigation, teachers and pupils find British English to be a bit “snobbish” while American English can sound a bit “cocky” to them. This investigation concludes that the two major influences on the pupils are their teachers and different kind of media.

All English language teachers are pronunciation teachers. Nobody can speak a language without pronouncing, and even if teachers ignore pronunciation in the classroom, they give the message that their learners' pronunciation is satisfactory, or that pronunciation doesn't matter. Questionnaires and needs analysis procedures frequently reveal that learners regard pronunciation as a high priority - often much more so than teachers - and it isn't difficult to appreciate the reasons for this: in spoken interaction, pronunciation is often the first barrier to intelligibility, and uncertainty about pronunciation is often a major reason for learners' lack of confidence in speaking.

Many teachers would like to offer their learners more help and support with pronunciation, but feel that they lack the necessary knowledge and skill, or that their own pronunciation is not sufficiently good. In other words, pronunciation is an area where teachers as well as learners often suffer from lack of confidence. The era of

English as an international language has also raised questions about the goals and models for pronunciation:

- What constitutes 'good' pronunciation?
- Should learners aim to sound as native-like as possible?
- If so, which native accents should they aspire to emulate?
- And if not, what are appropriate and achievable targets?
- What types of pronunciation can serve as useful models for learners to base themselves on?

It is very difficult for learners to achieve a pronunciation that sounds like a native speaker's. Discussions of the pronunciation of English as an international language have emphasized the fact that native-like pronunciation is also unnecessary for many learners, and may indeed not be wanted. It has been suggested that intelligibility is a more appropriate objective than conformity to any pre-existing model. Proposals have been made for an agenda of high-priority features which are particularly important for intelligibility. These include consonant sounds (excluding 'th' sounds, which are often difficult for learners of English, but unimportant for intelligibility), consonant clusters (except at the ends of words), contrasts between long and short vowels, and tonic stress. Features which are less important for intelligibility, such as precise vowel qualities, weak forms, and features of connected speech and pitch movements would not be included in teaching programmes. Intelligibility is a complex issue, however, and no doubt depends on different pronunciation features in different contexts, not to mention factors unconnected with pronunciation. Also, of course, learners have different priorities and aspirations - including for some (though probably a decreasing number) a wish to achieve a native-like pronunciation.

In order to be able to deal more effectively with pronunciation, teachers are likely to benefit from developing their knowledge and skills in the following areas:

1. Understanding how speech sounds are produced, how languages make systematic contrastive use of sounds, which sequences of sounds occur in particular languages, how sequences of sounds are modified in connected speech, and which patterns of stress, rhythm and intonation occur in English and other languages.
2. Predicting and identifying the aspects of pronunciation which are problematic for particular learners, drawing if possible on contrastive awareness of English and the learners' first language.
3. Identifying priorities for teaching, taking into consideration learner needs and ambitions, and sociolinguistic factors related to the role of English as an international language.

4. Distinguishing between aspects of pronunciation which are important for learners to acquire in their own speech, and aspects which are perhaps only important for recognition purposes in facilitating listening comprehension.

5. Implementing effective procedures for pronunciation teaching, drawing on the range of low- to high-technology resources available.

6. Integrating a concern for pronunciation into other classroom work whenever appropriate, as well as isolating specific pronunciation features for focused attention.

The problem of the work is concerned with varieties of English in different regions of Britain and various countries of the world. It is quite clear of course that dialectology is inseparably connected with sociolinguistics, the latter deals with language variation caused by social difference and differing social needs; it studies the ways language interacts with social reality.

We propose now a definition of this field of science: Sociolinguistics is the branch of linguistics which studies different aspects of language - phonetics, lexis and grammar with reference to their social functions in the society. The aim is to explain language phenomena in connection with factors outside the language faculty itself in terms of large-scale social structure and in terms of how people use language to communicate with one another.

Though in the past fifteen years Sociolinguistics has come of age and is a fast expanding and increasingly popular subject it should be fair to mention here that language has always been viewed as a social phenomenon, the most important means of human intercourse. So it is evident that language is indissolubly linked with the society; in it we can see a faithful reflection of the society in which people live.

It is quite clear, of course, that such fields of science as linguistics, sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics are inseparably linked in the treatment of various language structures. For example, the subject matter of ethnolinguistics gradually merges into that of anthropological linguistics and that into sociological linguistics and that into stylistics, and the subject matter of social psychology.

Some scholars consider functional stylistics to be a branch of Sociolinguistics since it studies the distinctive linguistic characteristics of smaller social groupings (such as those due to occupational class, age and sex differences).

In the case of English there exists a great diversity in the spoken realization of the language and particularly in terms of pronunciation. The varieties of the language are conditioned by language communities ranging from small groups to nations. Now speaking about the nations we refer to the national variants of the language. In then - treatment we follow the conception of A.D. Schweitzer. According to him national language is a historical category evolving from conditions of economic and political concentration which characterizes the formation of a nation. In other words national

language is the language of a nation, the standard of its form, the language of a nation's literature.

It is common knowledge that language exists in two forms: written and spoken. Any manifestation of language by means of speech is the result of a highly complicated series of events. The literary spoken form has its national pronunciation standard. A «standard» may be defined as «a socially accepted variety of a language established by a codified norm of correctness».

Today all the English-speaking nations have their own national variants of pronunciation and each of them has peculiar features that distinguish it from other varieties of English.

It is generally accepted that for the «English English» it is «Received Pronunciation» or RP; for «The American English» - «General American pronunciation»; for the Australian English - «Educated Australian» (we shall speak about it in detail later in the book).

Standard national pronunciation is sometimes called an «orthoepic norm». Some phoneticians, however, prefer the term «literary pronunciation».

Though every national variant of English has considerable differences in pronunciation, lexis and grammar, they all have much in common which gives us ground to speak of one and the same language - the English language.

It would not be true to say that national standards are fixed and immutable. They undergo constant changes due to various internal and external factors. Pronunciation, above all, is subject to all kinds of innovations. Therefore the national variants of English differ primarily in sound, stress and intonation. It is well-known that there are countries with more than one national language, the most common case being the existence of two national languages on the same territory. For this Canada will be an example, where two different languages - English and French - form the repertoire of the community.

It may be well to state that every national variety of the language falls into territorial or regional dialects. Dialects are distinguished from each other by differences in pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary. We must make clear that, when we refer to varieties in pronunciation only, we use the word «accent». So local accents may have many features of pronunciation in common and consequently are grouped into territorial or area accents. In Britain, for example, Yorkshire, Lancashire and Cheshire accents form the group of «Northern accent». We must admit, however, that in most textbooks on phonetics the word «dialect» is still used in reference to the regional pronunciation peculiarities, though in the latest editions both in this country and abroad the difference in terms «dialects and accents» is generally accepted. As we see, those terms should be treated differently when related to different aspects of the language. It is, however, true that there is a great deal of overlap between these

terms. For certain geographical, economic, political and cultural reasons one of the dialects becomes the standard language of the nation and its pronunciation or its accent - the received standard pronunciation. This was the case of London dialect, whose accent became the «RP» («Received Pronunciation») of Britain.

It has been estimated that the standard pronunciation of a country is not homogeneous. It changes in relation to other languages, and also to geographical, psychological, social and political influences. In England, for example, we distinguish «conservative, general and advanced RP».

As a result of certain social factors in the post-war period - the growing urbanization, spread of education and the impact of mass media, Standard English is exerting an increasing powerful influence on the regional dialects of Great Britain. Recent surveys of British English dialects have revealed that the pressure of Standard English is so strong that many people are bilingual in a sense that they use an imitation of RP with their teachers and lapse into their native local accent when speaking among themselves. In this occasion the term diglossia should be introduced to denote a state of linguistic duality in which the standard literary form of a language and one of its regional dialects are used by the same individual in different social situations. This phenomenon should not be mixed up with bilingualism that is the command of two different languages. In the case of both diglossia and bilingualism the so-called code-switching takes place. In recent years the effect of these forms of linguistic behavior is studied by sociolinguists and psychologists.

British sociolinguists divide the society into the following classes: upper class, upper middle class, middle class, lower middle class, upper working class, middle working class, lower working class. The validity of this classification is being debated in sociolinguistics. The problem of social stratification and of group theory has only recently been tackled by the science of sociology. The serious study of social dialects must be proceeded, or at least accompanied by significant advances in sociology and especially in the more precise definition of the notions, such as class, nation, nationality, society, language community, occupation, social group, social setting, occupational group, and so on.

So in the light of social criteria languages are «characterized by two plans of socially conditioned variability - stratification, linked with societal structure, and situational, linked with the social context of language use».

Having had our main terms straightened we may speak now of the «language situation» in terms of the horizontal and vertical differentiations of the language, the first in accordance with the spheres of social activity, the second-with its situational variability.

It is evident that the language means are chosen consciously or subconsciously by a speaker according to his perception of the situation, in which he finds himself.

Hence situational varieties of the language are called functional dialects or functional styles and situational pronunciation varieties - situational accents or phonostyles.

It has also to be remembered that the language of its users varies according to their individualities, range of intelligibility, cultural habits, sex and age differences. Individual speech of members of the same language community is known as idiolect.

Now it would be a perfectly natural thing to say that language in serving personal and social needs becomes part of the ceaseless flux of human life and activity. Human communication cannot be comprehended without recognizing mutual dependence of language and context. The mystery of language lies, if nowhere, in its endless ability to adapt both to the strategies of the individual and to the needs of the community, serving each without imprisoning either. This is what makes sociolinguistics as a science so important. In this book, though, we shall focus our attention on territorial modifications of English pronunciation viewing them as an object of sociolinguistic study.

The development of American English on the American continent has a comparatively short history. The conditions under which it developed were peculiar and quite unlike those under which the English language developed in Great Britain.

It is generally assumed that American English, in its spoken form, is essentially Southern English Standard of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries as modified locally in the course of the last century or two. The linguistic evidence for a historical connection between American speech of the North and West and that of Northern England on the one hand, and between the speech of Eastern New England and the pronunciation of the South of England on the other hand, is well supported by the history of American colonization, of the Westward movement, and of later immigration.

Though the details are complex and obscure, it is known that early settlers of New England and most of the central Atlantic coast were largely populated by people of the Southern and Eastern part of England. Those who settled Pennsylvania and Southern New Jersey came from the north of England. During the first half of the eighteenth century a large group of Germans came to America and settled throughout Pennsylvania (they are known as the Pennsylvania Dutch). A group of Welsh immigrants also settled in an area just west of Philadelphia. These settlements were supplemented by the arrival of the Scotch and Scotch-Irish whose speech was similar to that of the North of England.

Thus, differences in American speech represented differences in British speech from the outset. Later settlers also reflected later usage in the British Isles.

During the centuries in which the migrations were moving to the west of the country, the original settlements maintained a contact with Britain which the western settlers lost. Cities of the East coast long maintained their contact with London, and the Southern gentry continued to go to England for their education. Ships which arrived in Boston and other

eastern cities brought new fashions in speech from across the Atlantic. These new fashions in speech rarely reached the west.

The foundations of most of diversities in American pronunciation were thus laid during the colonial period. Some of the present differences in American pronunciation are attributed to that period as well. American English pronunciation (AE) of today is by no means homogeneous.

Geographically the Eastern type includes New England east of the Connecticut River. The Southern type includes Virginia, North Carolina, South Carolina, Tennessee, Florida, Georgia, Alabama, Mississippi, Arkansas, Louisiana, Texas and parts of Maryland, West Virginia, Kentucky and Oklahoma. General American includes the rest of the US -the language which may be heard, with only slight variations,

As early as the fifteenth century linguistic evidence shows that British dialects of Southern English were dropping the traditional "r" before consonants or at the end of words. In seventeenth and eighteenth centuries the vocalization of "r" became a characteristic feature of Standard English. It became fashionable in educated circles when the American colonies received their great influx. Thus, the earliest American settlements showing the strong imprint of Southern English dialects as well as Standard English, were marked by the characteristic loss of "r", which more northerly English dialects as well as later settlements extending further inland, retained. By far the largest part of the USA today continues to use this "r" sound in all positions.

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